

was reduced by 42%), resulting in yield (5.4 t/ha) significantly higher than that of the nonweeded control (3.1 t/ha). Thiobencarb with one hand weeding yielded 5.8 t/ha, two hand weedings yielded 6.2 t/ha, and the weed-free check, 6.0 t/ha. Next were 1 kg 2, 4-D EE/ha and 1.5 kg butachlor granules/ha.

Butachlor EN and Anilofos EC were not effective, probably because rain followed treatment. In cost-benefit ratio, 2 hand weedings gave an extra return of \$291; thiobencarb, \$234; and thiobencarb with one hand weeding, \$250, over the nonweeded control. Two hand weedings at the prevailing labor wage (\$0.84/d) was cheaper than the most promising herbicides, but labor availability is a limitation. □

Effect of herbicides on weed control in transplanted rice. Pantnagar, India, 1984.

Treatment	Concentration ^a (%)	Dose (k/ha)	Yield (t/ha)	Weed dry weight at harvest (g/m ²)
Hand weeding twice	—	—	6.2	0
Weed-free check	—	—	6.0	0
Thiobencarb + one weeding	—	—	5.8	42
Thiobencarb	10 G	1.5	5.4	164
Thiobencarb	10 G	1.0	4.2	229
2,4-D EE	4G	1.0	4.7	150
2,4-D EE	4G	0.8	3.9	211
Butachlor	5G	1.5	4.6	266
Butachlor	5G	1.0	3.7	282
Pendimethalin	5G	1.5	4.1	265
Pendimethalin	5G	1.0	3.6	254
Oxyfluorfen	0.35 G	0.15	4.1	242
Oxyfluorfen	0.35 G	0.1	3.2	287
Anilofos ^b	30 EC	0.4	3.7	263
Anilofos ^b	30 EC	0.3	2.5	298
Butachlor ^b	50 EN	1.5	3.1	295
Butachlor ^b	50 EN	1.0	3.1	260
Nonweeded control	—	—	3.1	397
LSD 5%			2.0	

^aG = granule, EC = emulsifiable concentrate, EN = emulsion. ^bRain followed spraying.

Weed species occurring in rice seedling nurseries in Guimba, Nueva Ecija, Philippines

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We surveyed the weeds in farmers' rice seedling nurseries in Barangay Bantug, Guimba, Nueva Ecija, Philippines, in the 1985 wet and 1986 dry seasons.

In the wet season, 17 species belonging to 13 genera and 7 families were recorded in 17 seedling nurseries; grasses and sedges accounted for 70.6% of the species (see table). In the dry season, nine species belonging to six genera and two families (five species of Poaceae, and four of Cyperaceae) were recorded in three seedling nurseries.

The most commonly occurring species in both seasons were *Echinochloa glabrescens*, *Paspalum distichum*, *Fimbristylis miliacea*, *Scirpus supinus*, *Echinochloa*

Weed species recorded in rice seedling nurseries in Guiriba, Nueva Ecija, Philippines, 1985-86 wet and dry seasons.

Weed species	Family	Wet season, 1985 (17) ^a	Dry season, 1986 (3) ^a
<i>Cynodon dactylon</i> (L.) Pers.	Poaceae	+	—
<i>Cyperus difformis</i> L.	Cyperaceae	+	+
<i>Cyperus iria</i> L.	Cyperaceae	+	—
<i>Cyperus rotundus</i> L.	Cyperaceae	+	+
<i>Echinochloa colona</i> (L.) Link	Poaceae	+	+
<i>Echinochloa glabrescens</i> Munro ex Hook. f.	Poaceae	+	+
<i>Echinochloa oryzoides</i> (Ard.) Fritsch.	Poaceae	+	+
<i>Eclipta prostrata</i> (L.) L.	Asteraceae	+	—
<i>Fimbristylis miliacea</i> (L.) Vahl	Cyperaceae	+	+
<i>Ischaemum rugosum</i> Salisb.	Poaceae	+	+
<i>Lindernia antipoda</i> (L.) Alston	Scrophulariaceae	+	—
<i>Ludwigia octovalvis</i> (Jacq.) Raven	Onagraceae	+	—
<i>Monochoria vaginalis</i> (Burm. f.) Presl	Pontederiaceae	+	—
<i>Panicum repens</i> L.	Poaceae	+	—
<i>Paspalum distichum</i> L.	Poaceae	+	+
<i>Phyla nodiflora</i> (L.) Greene	Verbenaceae	+	—
<i>Scirpus supinus</i> L.	Cyperaceae	+	+

^aNumber of nurseries surveyed indicated in parentheses; + = present, — = absent.

oryzoides, and *Cyperus difformis*.

Weeds not controlled in the nursery compete with the rice seedlings, resulting in weak seedlings. The weeds

pulled with the rice seedlings also are transplanted. The grassy weeds, in particular, are highly competitive during crop growth. □

The International Rice Research Newsletter (IRRN) invites all scientists to contribute concise summaries of significant rice research for publication. Contributions should be limited to one or two pages and no more than two short tables, figures, or photographs. Contributions are subject to editing and abridgment to meet space limitations. Authors will be identified by name, title, and research organization.